

Supplemental table 1. Relationship between parapapillary retinal nerve fiber layer and ganglion cell-inner plexiform layer thickness, and visual field parameters with the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)-10 or Hamilton Depression Rating Scale

		PSS-10 (total)		Hamilton Depression Rating Scale(total)	
		r	P value	r	P value
RNFL thickness, μm	Average	-0.174	0.085	-0.145	0.153
	Superior	-0.102	0.301	-0.093	0.362
	Nasal	-0.112	0.269	-0.158	0.118
	Inferior	-0.228	0.023*	-0.108	0.289
	Temporal	0.025	0.804	-0.020	0.845
GCIPL thickness, μm	Average	-0.215	0.033*	-0.135	0.183
	Minimum	-0.194	0.054	-0.239	0.017*
	Superior	-0.192	0.058	-0.137	0.176
	Superonasal	-0.195	0.053	-0.094	0.352
	Inferonasal	-0.230	0.022*	-0.115	0.256
	Inferior	-0.267	0.008*	-0.204	0.043*
	Inferotemporal	-0.220	0.029*	-0.125	0.217
Superotemporal	-0.128	0.208	-0.094	0.354	
Visual field	MD	0.119	0.247	-0.073	0.481
	PSD	-0.060	0.558	0.265	0.009*

GCIPL, ganglion cell-inner plexiform layer; MD, mean deviation; PSD, pattern standard deviation; RNFL, retinal nerve fiber layer

r=Pearson's correlation coefficient

*Statistically significant values ($P < 0.05$) are in bold.